

Figure 1. Location of *Zostera marina* meadows, sampled within the Topsail Sound Intracoastal Waterway, North Carolina.

Figure 2. Labeling system of *Z. marina* flowering shoots. Rhipidia (shown in blue, teal, pink, and green colors) form branching structures on each flowering shoot. Spathes (i.e., inflorescences) of each rhipidium (shown only for Rhipidium 2 in varying shades of green) constitute a branch of a rhipidium and contain a spadix with flowers and eventually seeds.

APPENDIX

Table A1. Microsatellite forward and reverse primer sequences.

Primer Mix	Microsatellite Locus	Dye	Referred to as	Source	Primer Sequence (5' - 3')	n Alleles
A	CL559CONTIG	NED	ZM1	Oetjen et al. 2010	F: CCACTTCCGTAGTTGCTGTT R: CGATGAGGACGATGAGGAAT	7
	CL32CONTIG2	FAM	ZM2	Oetjen & Reusch 2007	F: AATCTGTTGCCACGAAGGAG R: TCACCTTCATCAAGCAGTCG	7
	ZOSMARGA-3	VIC	ZM5	Reusch et al. 1999	F: CGACGATAATCCATTGTTGTTGC R: GCTTTTCATTATCCAATAGTTTGC	7
	ZMC12075	PET	ZM8	Oetjen & Reusch 2007	F: CCTCTTTTTTCTCTCTCTCTCTCT R: CTTCTGCGAATGATGCCATA	8
	ZOSMARCT-19	FAM	ZM9	Reusch 2000	F: CCCAAGAAATATAAAATCGGGG R: CTTCTCCTTCGCGCGTAC	5
B	ZOSMARCT-3	VIC	ZM3	Reusch et al. 1999	F: TGAAGAAATCCCAGAAATCCC R: AGACCCGTAAAGATACCACCG	10
	CL172CONTIG1	PET	ZM4	Oetjen et al. 2010	F: CTCCTGGACGCAGAAATATG R: GACAAACGTTAATTCAGAAACAAAA	8
	ZOSMARCT-12	FAM	ZM6	Reusch 2000	F: CGTTCATCTTGTCTCGTCC R: TTTCATTCCATTCCCACC	4
	ZMC19017	FAM	ZM7	Oetjen & Reusch 2007	F: TCGTCGAGAAAGAGGAGGAA R: TGTTCTGATTCCGTTCTCCA	8
	ZMC19062	NED	ZM10	Oetjen et al. 2010	F: CACTCTCCTCTTCCGTTTCG R: CAGGGGCCTTCTCTTACTC	4